

International Conference for
**Sustainable Design of the
Built Environment**
SDBE 2018

Proceedings

Editors

Heba Elsharkawy

Sahar Zahiri

Jack Clough

SDBE
Sustainable Development
of the Built Environment

University of
Strathclyde
Glasgow

9	Timothy O. Adekunle, Seth H. Holmes and Marialena Nikolopoulou	A Comparative Simulation of Thermal Performance in High-Rise Structural Timber Buildings	120 - 133
99	Sherine S.I. Tsang and Phillip Jones	Energy Performance Analysis of Large-Scale Public Buildings in China	134 - 145
129	Tala Awadallah and Omaimah Al-Arja	Comparative Study of energy consumption optimization for Educational buildings in Jordan	146 - 158
145	Sahar Abdelwahab, Mohammed Mayhoub and Ahmad El Kordy	Sunlight Directing System: The Effect of Surface Topology on Daylighting Performance	159 - 170
149	Alexander Kader	Upgrading the Energy Performance of Middle-Class Suburban Residential Buildings in the Gulf Region	171- 180
173	Omnya Saleh, Ahmed Khaled and Wagih Youssef	Light Shelf System in Energy Conservation to enhance daylight performances on Overcast condition in buildings	181 - 192
270	Nedhal Al-Tamimi and Abdultawab Qahtan	Assessment of Thermal Behaviour and Energy Consumption of Small Mosques in Hot-arid Climate of Najran City, KSA	193 - 202
272	Alex Marshall, Richard Fitton, Mo Benjaber and Will Swan	Investigating the Impact of Renewing Floor Coverings on the Energy Performance of Dwellings with Suspended Timber Floors, Tested under Controlled Conditions	203 - 214
33	Mohamed Faisal Al-Kazee	Implementation of BIM Technologies in Architectural Engineering Education	215 - 223
131	Amalia Banteli, Vicki E. Stevenson and Gabriela Zapata-Lancaster	Building Information Modelling (BIM) application in relation to embodied energy and carbon (EEC) considerations during design: A practitioner perspective	224 - 234
Chapter Two Education for Sustainability			22-32
<i>Paper Number</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Page Number</i>
18	Mahmoud Mohamadin, Ahmed Abouaiana and Yasser Sakr	Integrating Energy Performance Assessment Tools in Architectural Design Studio Education	236 - 244
42	Lamis Behbehani and Shahab Al-Bahar	Towards an ecological architectural education in Kuwait	245 - 256

Integrating Energy Performance Assessment Tools in Architectural Design Studio Education

Mahmoud Mohamadin ^a, Ahmed Abouaiana ^b and Yasser Sakr ^c

^a Assistant Lecturer, Arab Academy For Science & Technology, and Maritime Transport AASTMT.

mfmohamadin@gmail.com

^b PhD Candidate, Planning, Design and Technology of Architecture, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy.

ahmed.abouaiana@uniroma1.it

^c Former president of Helwan University.

ysakr60@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Contemporary architects rely on various digital and information technology tools starting from early design stages to construction and manufacturing stages. All these tools are reshaping our approach to architectural design, and consequently, to architectural education. As the environmental issues raise in our current approach to architectural design, available technologies are employed to solve these issues in every possible way. Departing from this point of view, energy performance assessment (EPA) tools seem to be useful in the architectural design pedagogy as it affects major design decisions and may completely alter the design process itself. The aim of this paper is to investigate empirically the potential of employing EPA tools in architectural design studio education with the focus on its impact on the design process. A workshop study was held in the design studios of the second year of the department of Architecture at the faculty of Fine Arts, Helwan University, Cairo, Egypt. A number of thirty six students were selected from the three studios of the department out of the total of hundred ninety eight students to participate in the study as an experimental group. Evaluation of the validity of this study was based on the students' feedback on the experiment through short structured questionnaire, and semi-structured interviews either individually, or in groups. The students of the experimental group could make better judgements on the environmental aspects in their design process. This confirms the applicability of the integration of EPA tools in architectural design studio education to enhance the understanding of the knowledge gained in environmental design projects. Furthermore, this study can help mapping out strategic recommendations for further studies for a model of implementing such tools in the design studio pedagogy.

Keywords: architectural education, design studio, energy performance assessment (EPA), ICT.

Introduction

ICT has been evolving dramatically what led to radical development in Architecture, Engineering & Construction (AEC) sector. In particular, computer software tools which are used in design process are being considered as a real expression of ICT in the field, such as Computer-Aided Design (CAD) and Building Information Modelling (BIM) (Moum, 2006) and (Penttilä, 2007). These tools identified in terms of its profound benefits (Khodeir, and Nessim, 2017) not only for competitiveness among architectural firms but also it influences directly to people's life specifically the rapid increase on energy demand issue where buildings' sector are responsible for about 40% of energy consumption (European Commission. 2017).

Therefore, BIM and EPA go hand in hand where EPA plays an essential act to enhance environmental performance of buildings particularly its capability to optimize energy consumption in conceptual design stage (Schlueter, A. and Geyer, P., 2018), Energy Plus simulation engine could be taken as an example, Furthermore, (Pagani & Chiesa, 2017) illustrates, as shown in Figure 1. the link between Energy Plus engine, and BIM such as the most used tools Revit.

Figure 1. The link between BIM and Energy Plus engine (Pagani & Chiesa. 2017)

Previous studies investigated the implications of the use of performance simulation tools in early design stage in practice (Attia, Gratia, De Herde, & Hensen, 2012) and (Castro & Alvarado, 2017) and others. It is rather important that in architectural education, the most rudimentary step which prepares architects for the near future, thus raising awareness of students in terms of energy efficient designs, in addition to push their capabilities of using simulation tools up from the beginning of design process. Integration of EPA tools in architectural education has already been adopted in several educational institutions (Nault, Moreno, Rey, and Andersen, 2017) yet the researchers concluded from the available litterateur that it is still limited to the environmental labs, and its application is not yet sufficiently extended to the design studio. This means that the students learn the use of these tools only for optimisation of spaces, or micro-climates after the design decision making stage. Unlike these practices, this study focuses on the potential of implementing these tools in early design stages, and its implications on the design process in terms of form, and tectonics.

Methodology

Due to the student-centered approach intended in this study, ethnographic research method was adopted, where the researchers observe and interact with the study's participants in their real-life environment for the purpose of enabling them to understand as much as possible about the study population (Balsiger & Lambelet, 2014). The study was implemented on a case study in the design studio of the second year at the department of Architecture at the faculty of Fine Arts, Helwan University, Cairo, Egypt. The study took the form of a workshop, where a number of thirty six students were selected from the three studios of the department to participate in the study as an experimental group. They represented the three formal design studios that contained a total number of students of hundred ninety-eight. Participants were gathered in one design studio setting upon a request arranged with the responsible professors of the three studios. The students were told that participation in the study was not obligatory, and that it would not affect their evaluation throughout the course.

The researchers limited the study's application to Autodesk FormIt platform, an architectural modelling software for architects to sketch, collaborate, analyse and revise early-stage design concepts. It allows users to create architectural modelling for tablet, web, and windows, and it has the ability to design with intelligence by connecting to other Autodesk apps to conduct an early analysis of space, energy and solar ("Autodesk FormIt"),

in addition to other differentiators that we are not taking into our consideration in this study.

Since all EPA tools are based on 3D digital modelling, experimental group pre-selection criterion was based on the student basic knowledge of 3D digital modelling software. Additionally, other factors were taken into consideration; (i) Express of interest of the student, (ii) Distribution of the selected students on the three studios of the department as follows: from studio 1, 12 selected out of 67, from studio 2, 16 selected out of 68, and studio 3, 8 selected out of 69 as shown in (Annex 2).

The experimental group had a brief introduction to the software, and a quick training for one week to ensure they understand how to start to apply it on their projects, while the rest of the students were left to work on the project with the ordinary help and guidance of their tutors, but without the help of any simulation tool.

The term architectural design process means a methodological series of steps that comprise data collection, conceptualization, schematic design, design development, and execution design documents. The workshop focused on the schematic design phase of the project, specifically the phase so called form generation phase. Each one of the participating students in the experimental group was asked to conduct the necessary simulations on the building forms they propose using Autodesk FormIt software until they reach an optimal composition in terms of sun exposure, and shadow on masses. The students were then encouraged to try to make their design decisions based on the simulation results either in form generation, or in façade treatment.

A short structured questionnaire on environmental performance assessment tools was designed, and it was distributed in the beginning, and at the end of the project on the experimental group in order to measure their awareness level of these tools, and to investigate if there was any significant differences. Semi- structured interviews took place as well to discuss the students' feedback on the experiences they gained through the workshop, and how this influenced their way in thinking and acting towards environmental design processes.

The Project

The project held in this design studio was assigned by the teaching staff of the second year of Architecture at the department of Architecture in the Faculty of Fine Arts, Helwan University. It was a residential villa for an artist; musician, painter, or sculptor etc. and it was located in a coastal area with a waterfront in the North direction. The building shouldn't have exceeded three stories, and the architectural program consisted of the following spaces: Villa reception halls, kitchen, guest toilet, two bedrooms with bathroom, master bedroom with private bathroom, family living space, and finally, an atelier for the artist. The form generation process assigned by the teaching staff was based on the formation, deformation, and transformation of an original geometry of a cube with the dimensions of 12m X 12m X 12m. The students were asked to conduct trials for the form generation that may include, but not limited to; addition, subtraction, subdivision, cracking, rotation, shifting, stacking, layering, or twisting, until they would reach a form composition that corresponds to both the functional requirements, as well as the contextual constraints, figure 2 depicts some samples of students work before the interventions.

Figure 2. Examples of the students' work before the intervention.

This design process that is based on the formation and superimposition of masses seemed to be going in line with the proposed hypothesis of this study. For instance, it gave the possibility of integrating the solar analysis of Autodesk FormIt software in the form generation process, which affected the design decisions made by the students in this phase. Students could apply modifications to the form to ameliorate it in terms of its relationship with the sun path around the masses, building faces exposure to the sun, and shade and shadow on building façades according to the results of the solar analysis that gave a better understanding of these considerations.

The Intervention

The workshop took place on weekly basis, with two sessions each week, and in a total of four sessions. The research team started its intervention to the project with an introductory lecture on Autodesk FormIt software and its instructions. Purpose, aim, and objectives of the workshop were discussed, the work plan throughout the workshop timeline was handed out, and the selection of the participant students was done. Participant students were given instructions on the program installation, tutorials, and resources.

The second session was an in-class training on the detailed instructions to use FormIt software either for 3D modelling, or for solar analysis. Figure 3 illustrates examples of the students' 3D FormIt models.

Figure 3. Examples of the students' FormIt models.

The third session comprised a lecture regarding the following considerations; Firstly, the role of material's thermal transmittance (U-Value) for both of opaque and transparent parts of building envelope. Secondly, window to wall ratio (WWR). Thirdly, creating shading through using simple shading devices and massing. Eventually, the role of orientation of spaces. Then the time left was dedicated to the form generation process.

Each student, using Autodesk FormIt, created his/her initial form previously prepared during their course in the design studio. The aim of this phase was to apply the solar analysis on the form composition and explore the relations, and implications of the sun on the building different façades, highlighting the relationship between the environmental forces and building form generation. In this phase, students were asked to reflect on the results of the

simulation, the problems they have encountered, and their suggestions toward improvements of such implications.

This lead to the application of some modifications to the preliminary form in and ongoing process between simulation and modification. This is exactly what we can call the simulation-based form generation process, Figure 4 shows an example of projects where form has been generated due to environmental aspects.

Figure 4. Two examples of students' projects.

The fourth and last session was a follow up session to explore more adjustments to the design according to the functional and contextual forces, and recommendations for the skin and roof treatments. Table 1 summarizes the work plan in Annex 1.

Discussion of Results

A short structured questionnaire was distributed on the experimental group through the online platform of Google forms. Students' attention was drawn to the fact that the questions were not exclusive and we're used to help them reflect on what environmental considerations may comprise. It consisted of three questions on whether the student knows or not the worst orientation for buildings in Egypt (figure 5), the height of the sun inclination angle in summer and winter (figure 6), and lastly, whether the student have ever used EPA tools before (figure 7). Nineteen students out of thirty six students responded to the questionnaire. The results of the questionnaire are shown in the following figures.

Figure 5. Response of solar latitude angle height

Figure 6. Response of orientation

Figure 7. Response of using EPA tools

Figure 5 depicts that fifteen students are aware enough that the solar latitude angle in summer is higher than in winter. while figure 6 shows that more than of half of the sample selected southern orientation as the worst façade orientation in Egypt, twelve students chose southwest, three students chose west, south east and north were selected by one student for each, and finally, one students said that *“There is not a worst standard orientation. It depends on space’s function and uses”*.

Eventually figure 7. Illustrates that all of the sample group except one student have never used EPA tools before.

The results of the study showed some interesting findings on the students' approach to architectural design before and after the experiment.

The attendance throughout the four sessions accounted by an average of 75% to 90%. Since the study was conducted on a case study of sophomore architectural students, a lack of environmental competencies was normally expected to show up, and it was noticed that by the end of the workshop the students of the experimental group expressed their satisfaction of the new competencies gained from it, and how it was relatively easier for them to understand these aspects.

Semi-structured interviews were held with the students during and in the end of the workshop. It is worth mentioning that the intervention started in a late phase of the project's design stage, which left a very limited time for the workshop to be conducted, therefore, and another round of interviews was held after the end of the semester in July 2018. Some interesting comments raised up during the interviews and discussions with the students about their feedback on the experiment. After having encountered the integrated approach of using solar analysis as a design support tool, and after having obtained the results of the simulations conducted on the masses of their projects, some of the students stated that they decided to make a critical decision of not only applying modifications, but to completely change their mass composition to effectively respond to these environmental considerations.

Mainly, the comments of the majority of the students were about the knowledge gained from this experience. These are such as; the importance of buildings orientation and that the correct choice of façades orientation, which is not a constant decision in all situations, but it depends on several considerations, thus building location, and function of spaces.

Another important point highlighted by the students was the possibility of using solar analysis simulations to conduct numerous trials in a relatively short time to choose an optimal mass composition in terms of solar exposure, and shade and shadows. In addition, some students commented on the usefulness of taking into consideration the environmental aspects in such an early stage of the design process where decisions could be crucial and could lead to major changes in the design output. However, two students out of the 36 participants were neutral regarding any advantages from this workshop.

Conclusion

In conclusion, ICT showed its effectiveness in all the architectural process so far starting from data collection to construction and fabrication. As investigated from literature, EPA tools can play a crucial role in early design stages as a decision support tool in architectural practice, and this has been confirmed in this study on the educational level. The study showed that even in a context of sophomore students environmental competencies can be enhanced remarkably using simple, yet effective EPA tools in the design studio. The study pays the attention to the fact that implementing these tools in the design studio of sophomore students is extendable to senior level students, but the researchers argue that this integration can face difficulties if applied on a freshman students level due to the lack of knowledge regarding this subject of matter.

Authors Contributions

Energy Performance Assessment Tools in Architectural Design: (Abouaiana, A)
Architectural Design Studio Education: (Mohamadin, M.)
Empirical Study: (Research Team)

Acknowledgement

The research team thanks Prof. Dr. Amal Ahmed Abdou, the head of Architecture Department, and all the teaching staff of the second year of Architecture at the faculty of Fine Arts, Helwan University in Cairo, Egypt, for giving the opportunity to implement this study within their design studios.

References

- Attia, S., Gratia, E., De Herde, A. and Hensen, J.L., 2012. Simulation-based decision support tool for early stages of zero-energy building design. *Energy and buildings*, 49, pp.2-15. [Accessed December 2017].
- Autodesk FormIt. (n.d.). Retrieved December 10, 2017, from <http://formit360.autodesk.com/> [Accessed December 2017].
- Balsiger, P., Lambelet, A. 2014, Participant Observation. In D. Della Porta (Ed.), *Methodological Practices in Social Movement Research* (pp. 144-172). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Beetham, H. and Sharpe, R. eds., 2013. *Rethinking pedagogy for a digital age: Designing for 21st century learning*. routledge.[Accessed October 2017].
- Bonilla Castro, A. and García Alvarado, R., 2017. BIM-Integration of solar thermal systems in early housing design. *Revista de la Construcción*, 16(2).
- Chung, D.H., 2014, July. Developing building performance in the comprehensive design studio. In ARCC Conference Repository.[Accessed November 2017]
- European Commission. 2017. Buildings. [ONLINE] Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/buildings> . [Accessed 7 November 2017].
- Kalay, Y.E., 2008, January. The Impact of Information Technology on Architectural Education in the 21st Centand Van der Veer, P., 1998, January. The role of ICT as a partner in Architectural Design Education. In *Computers in Design Studio Teaching EAAE/eCAADe International Workshop Proceedings* (pp. 139-146).[Accessed October 2017].
- Khodeir, L.M. and Nessim, A.A., 2017. BIM2BEM integrated approach: Examining status of the adoption of building information modelling and building energy models in Egyptian architectural firms. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal* [Accessed November 2017].
- Moum, A., 2006. A framework for exploring the ICT impact on the architectural design process. *Journal of Information Technology in Construction (ITcon)*, 11(30), pp.409-425. Vancouver. [Accessed November 2017].
- Nault, É., Aguacil Moreno, S., Rey, E. and Andersen, M., 2017. Energy performance analysis in interdisciplinary education—Lessons learned from a simulation-based teaching approach. In *PLEA 2017 Edinburgh-Design to Thrive* (No. EPFL-CONF-228844).
- Oliver, R., 2002. The role of ICT in higher education for the 21st century: ICT as a change agent for education. Retrieved April, 14, p.2007. [Accessed October 2017].
- Pagani, R. and Chiesa, G. eds.. 2017. *Urban data: Tools and methods towards the algorithmic city*. FrancoAngeli.. [ONLINE] Available at:<https://books.google.com.eg>.
- Penttilä, H., 2007. Early architectural design and BIM. *Computer-Aided Architectural Design Futures (CAADFutures) 2007*, pp.291-302. Vancouver.[Accessed November 2017].
- Reffat, R., 2007. Revitalizing architectural design studio teaching using ICT: Reflections on practical implementations. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 3(1), p.39. [Accessed October 2017].
- Schlueter, A. and Geyer, P., 2018. Linking BIM and Design of Experiments to balance architectural and technical design factors for energy performance. *Automation in Construction*, 86, pp.33-43. [Accessed October 2017].

Wang, T., 2009. Rethinking teaching with information and communication technologies (ICTs) in architectural education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 25(8), pp.1132-1140. [Accessed October 2017].

Wang, T., 2009. The transformational promise of information and communications technologies (ICTs) for the professional education of architects. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 12(3), p.206. [Accessed October 2017].

Yang, X., Zhao, L., Bruse, M. and Meng, Q., 2012. An integrated simulation method for building energy performance assessment in urban environments. *Energy and Buildings*, 54, pp.243-251. Vancouver. [Accessed November 2017].

(Annex A) Table 1. Work plan for integrating EPA tools in the design studio.

Session / Date	Teaching Activity	Content
Session 1 / Week 1: Monday, November 27, 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introductory Lecture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research team introduction. ● Study purpose, aim, and objectives. ● Work plan throughout the course timeline. ● Introduction to FormIt software, tutorials and resources, and program installation. ● Selection of participants.
Session 2 / Week 1: Wednesday, November 29, 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lecture on FormIt ● In-class training session 	Detailed instructions to use FormIt software: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 3D modelling. ● Energy Assessment.
Session 3 / Week 2 : Monday, December 4, and Wednesday, December 6, 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Form generation ● In-class work sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Highlighting the relationship between the environmental forces and building form generation.
Session 4 / Week 2: Monday, December 4, and Wednesday, December 6, 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Design development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Follow up sessions. ● Design adjustment according to the functional and contextual forces. ● Skin and roof treatments ● Plans, and sections.

(Annex B) Tables 2&3. Experimental group participants.

No.	Name	Studio
1	Ahmed Elgunidy	1
2	Ahmed Saleh	1
3	Ahmed Sayed	1
4	Alaa Amr	1
5	Ann Adeeb	1
6	Doaa Khalifa	1
7	Dreem Atallah	1
8	Esraa Hany	1

No.	Name	Studio
9	Hazem Abdelmalek	1
10	Toaa Taher	1
11	Toka Azab	1
12	Toqa Nasser	1
13	Abded Mokhtar	2
14	Abdelrahman Mohamed	2
15	Hader Abo Bakr	2
16	Madonna Medhat	2

17	Maria Gerges	2
18	Mariam Goma	2
19	Marwa Emad	2
20	Maryam Raslan	2
21	Mazen Shazly	2
22	Menna Samy	2
23	Muhammad Yehia	2
24	Nadine Hamdy	2
25	Rim Hossni	2
26	Salma Ahmed	2

27	Sara Gamal	2
28	Virona Ihab	2
29	Manar El-Leithy	3
30	Merhan Mohamed	3
31	Ucif Mohamed	3
32	Walaa Yassin	3
33	Wessam Saud	3
34	Yasmeen Raffat	3
35	Yasmeen Mostafa	3
36	Youstina Ashraf	3